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THE ADEQUACY OF BRONCHOSCOPIC BIOPSY IN THE DETECTION OF EPIDERMAL GROWTH FACTOR RECEPTOR IN LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA

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INTRODUCTION: Adenocarcinoma (ADC) of the lung is the most common type of lung cancer. The most reliable method in detecting EGFR mutations is real-time RT-PCR. It is recommended to sample three to five biopsy samples with a minimum of 200-400 preserved tumor cells (TC). The aim of this research is to determine are they bronchoscopic samples adequate for the determination of EGFR mutations in ADC.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: This retrospective analysis included of 60 patients with ADC diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica during the period 2010. to 2015. All cases included the identification of morphometric parameters, concentration of isolated DNA and EGFR mutation type.

RESULTS: Biopsy samples of an average size of 1.32 mm were most commonly obtained by transbronchial biopsy (63%). In 35% of cases there were one and two samples, $\geq 10\%$ of preserved tumors was found in 68% of cases. Considering the number of TC, the majority of cases (33%) were classified into Group V ($>200 \leq 500$ TC) and only 8% of cases in Group II ($>20 \leq 50$ TC). There was no statistically significant difference between the concentration of isolated DNA in wilde type and mutated EGFR ADC ($p=0.641$). Invalid results were found in 10% of cases. Only two mutations were detected (insertions in exon 20 and exon 21).

CONCLUSION: Bronchoscopic samples were adequate for the determination of EGFR mutations since the majority of bronchoscopic samples had more than 100 TC.